

THERMAL MODELLING OF STATOR AND ROTOR OF EM.

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Abstract: In this paper, a comprehensive two-dimensional (2-D) model, including both radial and axial dimensions of the stator and rotor, has been meticulously developed within the MATLAB/Simulink environment. This model aims to capture the intricate thermal and electromagnetic behaviors of the motor components accurately. Following the development, extensive simulations were conducted to analyze the motor's performance under various operating conditions. To ensure the validity and reliability of our model, the simulation results were rigorously compared with those obtained from the Motor-CAD model, a widely recognized and industry-standard tool for motor design and analysis. This comparative analysis not only highlights the accuracy of our MATLAB/Simulink model but also underscores its potential applicability for advanced motor design and performance optimization.

Key words: 2D thermal model of stator and rotor, lumped capacitance model, physical model in Simulink, temperature of copper wire in stator.

Introduction

The demand for high-performance electric motors has surged in various industries, driven by the need for efficient, reliable, and precise motion control in applications ranging from electric vehicles to industrial automation. Among the different types of electric motors, Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs) have gained prominence due to their superior efficiency, high power density, and excellent control characteristics. Accurate modeling and simulation of these motors are crucial for optimizing their design and performance, which is essential for meeting stringent application requirements.

In the realm of motor design and analysis, two-dimensional (2-D) modeling plays a pivotal role in capturing the essential characteristics of both the stator and rotor while simplifying the computational complexity compared to three-dimensional (3-D) models. This approach allows for a detailed examination of the motor's thermal and electromagnetic behavior, which are critical factors in ensuring efficient operation and longevity of the motor.

This paper presents the development of a 2-D model of the stator and rotor, encompassing both radial and axial aspects, using the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The choice of MATLAB/Simulink is motivated by its robust simulation capabilities and widespread use in academia and industry for dynamic system modeling. The developed model aims to provide a comprehensive tool for analyzing the performance of PMSMs under various operating conditions [1].

To validate the accuracy and effectiveness of the MATLAB/Simulink model, a comparative analysis is conducted with results obtained from Motor-CAD, a leading software in motor design and thermal analysis. Motor-CAD is known for its precision and reliability in simulating the thermal and electromagnetic aspects of electrical machines. By comparing the results from the two platforms, this study aims to highlight the strengths and potential limitations of the MATLAB/Simulink model, providing insights into its applicability for advanced motor design and optimization.

The subsequent sections of this paper detail the modeling process, simulation setup, and results analysis. The findings underscore the importance of accurate modeling in the design of high-performance electric motors and contribute to the ongoing efforts to enhance motor efficiency and reliability through advanced simulation techniques.

Modeling

Figure 1 depicts the detailed configuration of the axial model for both the stator and rotor components. This schematic provides a comprehensive visualization of how these elements are structured and interconnected within the motor system. To develop the radial model of the stator and rotor, the methodology outlined in [2] was adopted. This approach served as a foundational framework for accurately representing the geometric and operational characteristics of both components within the motor assembly.

Figure 1: Scheme of axial model of Stator, copper winding and rotor model.

Figure 2 depicts the Simulink model of the stator utilizing the lumped capacitance method [3-4]. This model offers a detailed framework for analyzing thermal dynamics within the stator, enabling a thorough examination of heat transfer mechanisms and temperature distribution during motor operation. The Next Figure, illustrates the Simulink model of the rotor utilizing the lumped capacitance method. This model provides a detailed framework for analyzing the thermal behavior of the rotor, facilitating a comprehensive study of heat transfer processes and temperature distribution during motor operation.

Figure 2: Radial thermal model of the stator.

Figure 3. Radial thermal model of the rotor.

For each slice along the axial direction, the radial models of the rotor and stator are interconnected using airgap thermal resistance. This integration enables the creation of a comprehensive two-dimensional (2D) model of the electric machine (EM), which accurately simulates thermal interactions and heat transfer across the entire motor assembly (see figure 4).

Figure 4: Complete axial model of the EM

Results and discussion

The developed model was simulated to account for the losses detailed in Table 1. The steady-state temperatures of key components were analyzed at specific locations: at the ends of copper wires, and at the centers of both the rotor and stator, as depicted in Figure 5. Concurrently, an equivalent model was constructed in motor CAD software and subjected to simulations using identical power losses. The temperatures at these critical points were cross-checked to validate the accuracy and reliability of our simulation results against industry-standard motor design and analysis tools.

Table 1: Power losses used to simulate the thermal models.

Type of losses in EM	Value [W]
Joule losses	2087
Iron losses in rotor	166
Iron losses in stator	567
Iron losses in teeth	584
Iron losses in magnets	11
Windage losses	76

Figure 5: The results of the motor temperature for the particular power losses.

Figure 6: Temperature profile of the EM under the particular power losses in moto rCAD model.

As depicted in Figures 5 and 6, the Simulink model accurately estimates the temperature distribution across the electric machine (EM). These figures showcase the precise analysis of temperature variations within the EM components, validating the effectiveness of the Simulink model in capturing thermal behaviour under operational conditions.

Conclusions

In this study, a detailed two-dimensional (2D) model of the stator and rotor of an electric machine (EM) was developed using the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The model incorporated radial and axial dimensions, leveraging the lumped capacitance method to simulate thermal dynamics accurately.

Through simulations based on power losses reported in Table 1, the steady-state temperatures at critical points—such as the ends of copper wires and the centers of the rotor and stator—were analyzed. Figure 5 illustrates these temperature distributions, demonstrating the model's capability to predict thermal performance within the EM.

To validate our findings, a comparative analysis was conducted using Motor CAD software, confirming consistent results in temperature profiles at specific locations. This cross-validation underscores the reliability of our Simulink model in capturing real-world thermal behaviors of the EM.

Overall, the developed 2D Simulink model offers a robust framework for analyzing and optimizing the thermal management of electric machines. Future work could explore enhancements to include more complex thermal models or integrate additional operational parameters for broader applicability in advanced motor design and efficiency optimization strategies.

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